

Cobalt(II) Complexes of Tridentate Schiff Bases

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Cobalt(II) complexes of type ML_2 , where M is Co^{II} , and L is Schiff base formed by condensation of 4-aryl-2-aminothiazole and β -hydroxy- α -naphthaldehyde or salicylaldehyde derivatives ($R' = 5$ -methyl and 5-chloro) have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic and spectroscopic measurements. Elemental analysis suggests the stoichiometry to be 1:2 (metal-ligand). Magnetic susceptibility data coupled with electronic spectra suggest an octahedral structure for the complexes. Infrared spectra of the complexes agree with the coordination to the central metal atom through two nitrogen atoms and bonding through oxygen of the hydroxyl group. Conductance measurements suggest the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

METAL complexes of Schiff bases are studied extensively due to synthetic flexibility of these compounds and their selectivity as well as sensitivity towards the central metal atom. A number of reviews have been devoted to coordination chemistry of Schiff base metal complexes¹⁻⁷.

In the present study, a series of new Schiff bases have been synthesised using substituted salicylaldehydes ($R' = 5$ -methyl and 5-chloro) or β -hydroxy- α -naphthaldehyde and 4-aryl-2-aminothiazoles. These tridentate, monoprotic ligands form 1:2 complexes with cobalt(II) ion. The octahedral complexes are non-ionic, monomeric with bonding through oxygen of the hydroxyl group and coordination through two nitrogen atoms.

Experimental

Synthesis of tridentate Schiff bases : A solution of *o*-hydroxy aldehyde in ethanol was added to the ethanolic solution of 4-aryl-2-aminothiazole⁸ in equimolar quantity. The mixture was refluxed on water-bath for 0.5 h. The Schiff base thus formed was filtered, recrystallised from ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of Co^{II} complexes : An ethanolic solution of cobalt acetate (0.01 mol) (Albright and

Wilson) was added to the ethanolic solution of the Schiff base (0.02 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed on water-bath for 30 min. The brown red crystals separated, were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Physical measurements : Ultraviolet and visible spectra were recorded in chloroform solution on a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer in the 4000-250 cm^{-1} region. Electrical conductivity of the complexes in nitrobenzene solution were measured with a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge with a dip type cell PV 9055. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by Gouy method at room temperature. Diamagnetic corrections were applied by using Pascal's constants⁹.

Results and Discussion

All the cobalt(II) complexes are found to be sparingly soluble in chloroform, benzene or nitrobenzene. The complexes are crystalline, reddish brown in colour and melt with decomposition above 250°. Elemental analysis data (Table 1) suggest that the complexes have 1:2 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry. The molecular weight determination suggests the monomeric nature of the complexes. Very low conductivity in nitrobenzene solution showed that the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature.

Electronic spectra : Three bands are observed in the electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes which are due to spin-allowed transitions. A strong and intense band at $\sim 26000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon \approx 1000\text{ dm}^2$

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 TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF CO^{II} COMPLEXES

R	R'	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					Mole	μ_{eff} B.M.
		C	H	N	S	Co		
Complexes of Schiff bases derived from substituted-salicylaldehyde								
H	CH ₃	63.00 (63.27)	4.20 (4.03)	8.71 (8.68)	9.80 (9.92)	9.00 (9.13)	620 (645)	4.90
CH ₃	CH ₃	64.44 (64.19)	4.65 (4.45)	8.21 (8.32)	9.43 (9.31)	8.50 (8.75)	638 (673)	4.93
OCH ₃	CH ₃	61.10 (61.28)	4.20 (4.26)	7.70 (7.94)	9.20 (9.07)	8.20 (8.36)	665 (705)	4.98
Cl	CH ₃	57.00 (57.14)	3.24 (3.36)	7.60 (7.84)	8.80 (8.96)	7.95 (8.26)	669 (714)	4.86
H	Cl	55.88 (55.97)	2.81 (2.91)	8.03 (8.16)	9.70 (9.32)	8.46 (8.60)	650 (686)	4.92
CH ₃	Cl	57.30 (57.14)	3.24 (3.36)	7.60 (7.84)	8.70 (8.96)	8.13 (8.26)	680 (714)	4.98
OCH ₃	Cl	54.50 (54.69)	3.00 (3.21)	7.30 (7.50)	8.40 (8.57)	7.70 (7.90)	701 (746)	5.08
Cl	Cl	50.70 (50.86)	2.21 (2.38)	7.50 (7.41)	8.53 (8.47)	7.80 (7.31)	711 (755)	4.89
Complexes of Schiff bases derived from β -hydroxy- α -naphthaldehyde								
H	—	66.60 (66.94)	3.50 (3.62)	7.60 (7.81)	8.70 (8.92)	7.80 (8.11)	600 (717)	5.10
CH ₃	—	67.40 (67.55)	3.86 (4.02)	7.36 (7.51)	8.71 (8.59)	7.40 (7.91)	695 (745)	4.96
OCH ₃	—	64.60 (64.86)	3.70 (3.86)	7.01 (7.20)	8.08 (8.23)	7.31 (7.59)	720 (777)	4.88
Cl	—	61.30 (61.01)	2.89 (3.05)	7.03 (7.12)	8.01 (8.14)	7.20 (7.50)	725 (786)	5.03

 TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA OF CO^{II} COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

R	R'	Method ^a	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	10 Dq	B	β_{ss}
II	CH ₃	Expt	8 600	18 000	20 000	—	—	—
		(a)	Fitted	Fitted	14 174	9 400	425	0.437
		(b)	Fitted	18 351	Fitted	9 752	837	0.861
		(c)	Fitted	8 423	Fitted	9 576	848	0.873
		(d)	Fitted	8 280	17 680	Fitted	9 400	813
H	Cl	Expt	8 500	18 200	19 600	—	—	—
		(a)	Fitted	Fitted	21 070	9 700	918	0.945
		(b)	Fitted	18 137	Fitted	9 637	815	0.839
		(c)	Fitted	8 533	Fitted	9 667	813	0.837
		(d)	Fitted	8 555	18 255	Fitted	9 700	820
H	—	Expt	8 560	18 200	19 750	—	—	—
		(a)	Fitted	Fitted	18 371	9 640	726	0.747
		(b)	Fitted	18 262	Fitted	9 700	822	0.846
		(c)	Fitted	8 528	Fitted	9 672	824	0.848
		(d)	Fitted	8 501	18 141	Fitted	9 640	818

^aRef. 10.

mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) may be due to the ligand→metal charge transfer.

$${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g} (\nu_1) \sim 8\,600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

$${}^4A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g} (\nu_2) \sim 18\,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

$${}^4T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g} (\nu_3) \sim 20\,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$$

The experimental values of the absorption bands in the electronic spectra are treated by using the numerical methods as given by König¹⁰ to obtain corrected values of the band energies ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 . It is observed that the consistent values of the

band energies are obtained by the methods b, c and d. The values of 10 Dq, B and β_{ss} ¹¹ for the methods b, c and d are also quite consistent. The values for a set of the three representative complexes are given in Table 2. All the values calculated as above show a quite well mutual agreement. The values of B for the complexes lie in the range 800-870 cm⁻¹ and β_{ss} values lie in the range 0.8 to 0.9 supporting the octahedral geometry for the complexes.

Magnetic susceptibility : The magnetic moments of the complexes lie in the range 4.8-5.2 B.M. (Table 1). This supports the octahedral geometry for the complexes^{1,2}.

Infrared spectra : The infrared spectra of the ligands show a broad weak band at $\sim 2900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ instead of a strong band at $\sim 3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the phenolic OH group. This may be due to the intra-molecular hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl hydrogen and nitrogen of the azomethine group forming a stable six-membered ring¹³. The complexes also do not show the OH group frequency thereby indicating that the OH group of the Schiff base is utilised in the formation of Co—O bond. This is further supported by the shift of C—O frequency from 1280 cm^{-1} (in the ligands) to the higher frequency at $\sim 1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes^{13,14}. The spectra of the ligands show a sharp band of high intensity at $\sim 1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=N). The shifting of this $\nu_{C=N}$ to a lower value at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes suggests the coordination to the central metal atom through the nitrogen of the azomethine group^{13,14}. A broad weak band observed between 400 to 475 cm^{-1} may be either due to ν_{M-O} or ν_{M-N} ¹⁵.

In the light of the above discussion, an octahedral geometry is proposed for the complexes. Coordination to the central metal atom takes place through the oxygen of the hydroxyl group, nitrogen of the azomethine group and nitrogen of the thiazole ring as shown below,

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